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Social Movements in India and Gandhi

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ABSTRACT

The long history of social movements clarifies that social movements are not a new phenomenon in India. But the studies of social movements have found significantly less attention in India. Survival of the fittest is the scientific theory that states that only those species will survive, which will fit according to the nature of a particular place. Human beings have always struggled for their survival. The struggle may be with nature, the environment or within the society. And, the study of social movements is the study of human struggle for survival. Social movements have various kinds like some time; they bring structural changes in the society and become the cause of social transformation. Social conflicts play an essential role in the emergence of social movements. In this way, social movements are the manifestations of the social problem.

Social movements in India are as old as human civilization. When we study the history of India, we find that social movements in ancient India occurred in the form of religious movements. Buddhism and Jainism emerged in ancient India because of the religious movement. In modern Indian society, the colonial intervention provided reasons for the emergence of social movements. Social movements occurred because of political consciousness among the various ethnic groups. After the foundation of the Indian National Congress, the Indian masses got leaders like Gandhi and Ambedkar, who participated in social movements. Gandhi led political as well as social movements in India. On this ground, the paper is an attempt to understand the social movements in India. The article defines the conceptual understanding of social movements, history, types, and reasons. This paper emphasise on how Gandhi contributed to giving a new direction to the social movements in India? This paper will also focus on the use of Gandhi's philosophy of non-violence in social movements.

Keywords: *Social Movements, Colonial India, Religious Reform Movements, Lower Caste Movements, Nature of Social Movements, Gandhi and social movement.*

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INTRODUCTION

The social movements in India can be categorized into two phases; the first phase comprises pre-independent India, whereas the second phase covers post-independent India. The pre-Indian social movements were based on Marxist ideology and Gandhian ideology. In post-independent India, social movements continued to follow these two ideologies. But with the passing of time, Gandhian ideology received more attraction because of its non-violent principles. Several reasons played a significant role in the popularization of Gandhian ideology in post-independent social movements. The first reason was that the Indian government did many reforms such as; land-reforms and economic reforms to develop a national economic structure. These reforms directly benefited the common masses; therefore, the Indian masses adopted peaceful ways to get socio-economic and political rights. The second reason was that Independent India had a self-ruled government, and the reformers did not want to do an armed revolt against the government.

The post-independent social movements are essential because many communist leaders tried to mix communist ideology with Gandhian ideology. The main reason for this amalgamation of the fall of communist ideological relevance in India. After independence, the communist scholars tried to establish relations between communist ideology and Gandhian ideology so that they could be relevant in Indian society and Indian politics. Therefore, many social movements occurred in post-independent India, which communist activists led, but they claimed to follow Gandhian principles.

Definition of Social Movements:

The study of 'social movements' is in its formative stage in India. The sociologists did not pay more attention to this phenomenon in India. Social movements have been defined differently by different scholars. Some scholars have seen movement as an organisation or union. Ghanshyam Shah has argued:

A social movement must evince a minimal degree of organization, though this may range from a loose, informal or partial level of organization to the highly institutionalized and bureaucratized movement and the corporate group¹.

Different concepts related to social movements are the formation of ideologies, the source of identity, organisation and leadership, the event structure, the

internal dynamics and the social consequences. Social movements are based on organised efforts aiming at changes in social structure. For being an organised effort, social movements need an ideology for mobilising the masses and connecting with cultural change. Social movements can bring about social change and social mobility. These social changes and mobility are based on challenges, protest, confrontation, aggression and revolt. Therefore, protest-based social movements bring qualitative changes in the traditional structure of social relationships². Ananta Giri writes that 'the crises in representation' have played an essential role in the emergence of these social movements. The ecological movement has changed the discourse on social movements, and it has challenged the development of organisations. He further argues about the role of electronic communication in social movements³.

Debal K. Singharoy argues that social movements are organised collective mobilisation which tries to bring change in thoughts, values, beliefs, relationships, and major institutions in society or try to bring change in any structural element of the society. Touraine argues that social movements are the product of the realisation of history⁴. According to Ghanshyam Shah, social movements are revolt, rebellion, reform and revolution within the society⁵. Tilly and Wood presented their view about social movements in the context of England and America. They argued that the social movements occurred in these countries because of political and economic reasons. The industrial revolution in western countries increased the inequality among the society. According to Tilly and Wood, the development of capitalism is the leading cause of social movement⁶.

The conceptual problems in social movements:

The study of any new field of specialization needs some conceptualization. M.S.A. Rao has identified the five types of conceptual problems in social movements. The first conceptual problem is related to definition and classification of social movements, the second problem is related to the emergence of movements, the third problem is related to the formation of ideologies and establishing identities, the fourth problem is related with collective mobilization, organization, leadership, internal dynamics and routinization and the fifth problem is related to the nature of the consequences and changes in the wider society and culture⁷.

Rao makes a distinction between movements and non-movements. He argues that a social movement involves

collective action, brings either partial or total changes in the existing system, values and norms. However, he further contends about some limitations of the social movements. According to him, when a movement becomes an established institution, and it adopts a code of conduct, and sanctions for punishing deviants, in this situation, the movement becomes a part of the institutionalized system⁸. Nelson A. Pichardo has seen the elements of 'New' social movements at two levels. One is macro-historical, and the other is micro-historical elements of social movement. At the macro level, the new social movement paradigm concentrates on the relationship between the rise of contemporary social movements and the broader economic structure and the role of culture. At the micro-level, the paradigm identifies the issues and the personal behavior⁹. Partha Mukherji argues that social changes can happen only by mobilization, and mobilization brings structural changes. In other words, he says that social movement is a type of social conflict that has many different reasons. He looks the social conflicts as the product of manifestations of combined actions¹⁰.

Partha N Mukherji believes that social movements are helpful, enabling us to know more about social mobilization. Mukherji gives the example of the student movement, labour movement, religious revival movement, and peasants' movement. Mukherji gives four points that clarify his view. First, social movements are related to social change and social structure, but social change can also happen independently. Second, the social structure of a particular society is responsible for social movement. Third, social movements have a system. And fourth, social movements have consequences for the social structure of which they are products¹¹. Chesters and Welsh argue about anarchism's role in social movements that emerged in Europe in the 19th century. According to them, '*Anarchy is commonly understood in terms of the absence or breakdown of social order; advocates of anarchism promote voluntary forms of associations constitutive of social order independent of a state.*'¹²

Various Approaches to Social Movements:

There are various approaches to understand social movements like the Marxist approach, Gandhian approach, functional approach, resource mobilisation theory and relative deprivation theory. The Marxist approach provided fuel to the working class movements in various countries. Marxist approach states that society is the arena of social inequality. Therefore, Marxists

approach ties to explain how inequality contributes to the emergence of social movements. Marxism believes that private ownership and primitive accumulation of wealth, labour exploitation, economic inequality etc., contribute to the revolutionary social movements. The Marxist approach assumes that the capitalist forces like the bourgeoisie who have command over the production like machines, factories, media, education system etc., create the situation for the social movements. The Marxist approach focused on local collective action against capitalist powers in the early 20th century. After the Second World War, the Marxist approach sifted towards class conflict against global capitalism. The Marxist approach believes that the oppressed should be violent against exploiters because the exploiter class would hardly surrender without violence¹³.

The structural-functional approach of social movements brings the forefront analysis of industrial injustices and inequalities on which the contested politics is fought. This approach explains the formation of collective action, which means organising activities and actions for changing the existing structure. This approach illustrates that social movements occur because of the gap between the peoples' expectations and the government's facilities. Neil J. Smelser has explained six major structural factors which are responsible for the social movement. First, society is found to have a serious structural problem in which a person is forced to live with low living standards. In this situation, people become proactive to engage in collective mobilisation. Second, the strains that have been caused by social structure are responsible for the social movement. For example, in third world countries, social situations like exclusion, inequality, injustice, ethnic marginalisation etc., are consistently found to be the crucial factors behind the social movements. Third, Smelser argues that the strains and their explanation are also the important cause behind the social movements. Fourth, the existing disapprovals or such kinds of factors also contribute to the emergence of social movements. The fifth important factor behind the social movement is the mobilisation for action. It depends upon the leader how he explains the situation before those who are participating in the movement. And, the six-factor for the social movement is the lack of social control. Social control depends upon the government's response to the movement. The success of any social movement depends upon the mass controlling power. The structural-functional approach helps to explain the feminist movements¹⁴.

The Gandhian approach of social movements developed in South Africa against racial discrimination by the colonial government. This approach became popular in India because of its successful experiments in Indian peasant movements, class repression, British rule, untouchability, gender discrimination etc. The Gandhian approach advocated for peaceful struggle. Moral and ethical values are the guiding principles for the Gandhian approach to social movements. Certain methods like *satyagraha*, non-violence, *Sarvodaya* etc., guide the Gandhian approach. *Satyagraha*. *Satyagraha* is the weapon of the strong man, it never admits violence in any circumstances, and it emphasises truth. According to David Hardiman, 'Gandhi's *satyagraha* is dialogical resistance in which adversary is not considered as an enemy'¹⁵. Gandhian ideology emphasises truth, non-violence, Khadi, Charkha, Trusteeship etc. Gandhian approach believes in the heart and mind change of opponents rather than using violence. The entire Indian national movement led by Gandhi is an example of the use of the Gandhian approach. The Gandhian social movement approach has been successfully used by various leaders like the Bhoodan movement of Vinoba Bhave, the Chipko movement led by SundarlalBahoguna etc.

Resource Mobilization Theory is another fundamental approach that plays a vital role in social movements. According to this approach, substantial resources are essential for the success of any social movement. The well-defined antecedents to collective action like structural deprivation and strains, conflicts and contestation alone cannot cause social movements. The success of any social movement depends upon the effective and efficient use of the resources like human resources, social resources and financial resources. Internal and external resource mobilization contribute to the emergence of social movements¹⁶.

Types of social movements:

There are many types of social movements like backward classes, worker's, religious and sectarian movements, tribal movements, women's movements, peasant movements, student, and environmental movements. The lower caste movement and other backward class movements emerged in India during the 19th and 20th centuries. These movements were based on both religious as well as secular ideologies. These movements occurred in various parts of India¹⁷.

The workers' movement started in India during the colonial capitalist development. These movements happened because of the industrial development in India and the establishment of the railway. The workers have been classified into organised and unorganised sectors of formal and informal sectors¹⁸. Tribal movements have a very old history in India. Tribes considered themselves as a religious and civilised community. This community has always been considered a peaceful community because they did not interfere in the affairs of other social communities. They started movements after the establishment of the colonial government. The colonial government entered into the tribal area and applied the same laws applied to the other parts of India. Tribal people fought against the colonial government and Indian landlords¹⁹.

The women's movement is one of the most important types of social movement. This movement started during the Indian renaissance, which took place during the 19th century. Many social reformers put women's issues as a central concern in many social movements. Many social reformers like Ram Mohan Roy, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar, JyotibaFule, Ambedkar and Gandhi etc., indicated women's issues by their writings. Because of their efforts, women's movements started to take place in India²⁰. Ghanshyam Shah has studied student movements in India. He did a comparative study of student movements in Gujarat and Bihar²¹. Ramchandra Guha has studied environmental movement. There was a movement named 'Chipko', which emerged in Uttarakhand. This movement was very much concerned with the local people of Uttarakhand. This movement presented unity among the people, and therefore, it became a mass movement²².

History of social movements in India:

A social movement is not a new phenomenon in India. Many social movements had happened in India in the ancient and medieval periods. These social movements continue in modern times also. Historians like Irfan Habib argue about the religious movements in the medieval period and the emergence of new religions like 'Sikhism'²³. The same kind of social changes was seen in ancient India, and Buddhism and Jainism emerged. In ancient Indian society, the movements happened because of urban prosperity and class and caste distinction. Those people, who did movements in ancient India, had left their homes and lived as wanderers. They did it to achieve renunciation, which was not a new idea. The *Vedic tradition also performed the renunciation*. But

with time, the *Vedic* people had left the path of renunciation. Many evils entered into the *Vedic* people. Because of this, the new sects started movements, and many new sects came into being like; *Ajivikas*, *Buddhism*, *Jainism* and *Shaivism* etc. All these sects struggled against *Vedic* tradition and its evils and provided some new path to the people. Buddhism talked about women's rights, animal's rights, rights for nature etc. Jainism

Showed a good path to the people²⁴. These types of social movements can be called religious and sectarian movements. These religious or sectarian movements have the language of protest, innovation and expression of individuality²⁵.

In medieval India, many Muslim Sufi sects like *Chisti*, *Aouliya* and *Suhrawardi* came into existence, focusing on equality. During the 13th to 16th century, many Hindu *Bhakti* social reformers like Ramananda, Kabir, Nanak and Raidas etc., became popular. They taught the Indian masses to live with equality and respect for each other. A new religion, 'Sikhism' came into being at this time. This religion was the product of social movements. All the reformers of medieval India focused on the prayer of a single God, and equality for all human beings²⁶. In modern Indian society, the social movements started with the establishment of a colonial government. The colonial government played a significant role in making awareness among the Indian masses. After getting independence, many social movements occurred in India, and they continue in the present time also.

In colonial India, social movements became a widespread event because colonial powers used certain rules that became the cause behind the emergence of social movements in various parts of the country. The identical changes in the social movements before the colonial period to the pre-independent period were significant because, before the colonial period, social movements did not adopt violent nature and put religion in the centre of the movement. But during the colonial period, social movements left religious characteristics and did not hesitate to adopt a violent nature. Colonial intervention in the socio-economic and religious matters of Indians provided fuel to the social movements.

Gandhi and Social Movements:

Gandhi was an ordinary person when he reached South Africa. Gandhi's political ideas developed in South Africa, and he participated in various political and social movements. After coming back to India, Gandhi visited

various parts of the country and saw the situation of common people. Gandhi's first political activity in India was his participation in the Champaran peasant movement in Bihar. Here, peasant movements emerged against the *Tinkathiya* system in which peasants were forced to cultivate indigo on 1/3 part of agricultural land. In the same way, Gandhi led peasant movements in Kheda, Awadh and Bardoli. Peasant movements helped in the emergence of political awareness among the masses. The important quality of Gandhi's leadership was that he tried to follow the principle of non-violence in his movements to connect themselves with these movements. For instance, Gandhi advised the peasants of Awadh not to use violence, and he provided an oath to the peasant that they would not do violence²⁷.

Gandhi did not directly launch any religious reform movements by name, but he did many actions that can be considered religious reform. Though Gandhi had faith in Hinduism, he did not ignore the importance of other religions. The gist of all religions influenced his religious views. Bharatan Kumarappa compiled Gandhi's various writings which Gandhi wrote on religion. Kumarappa published them with the title, 'My Religion'. In this compiled work, Kumarappa argues that though Gandhi was born a Hindu, his Hinduism was his own. Gandhi did not believe in Hinduism that several extremist Hindu leaders propagated, but he adopted ancient *Sanatana* Hinduism. Gandhi took some principles from all religions; therefore, he could connect himself with all religions in India. Gandhi considered religion an integral part of human life; therefore, he said that 'no man can live without religion. Gandhi had faith in religion to the extent that he said that those who say they have nothing to do with religion have their argument like they breathe but have no nose. Gandhi never made a distinction among different religious faiths.

Gandhi said,

*"Religions are different roads converging to the same point. What does it matter that we take different roads, so long as we reach the same goal? In reality, there are as many religions as there are individuals."*²⁸

In this way, Gandhi used religious ideas in a broader sense. Since his childhood, Gandhi was more influenced by the Indian tradition, and his traditionalist view appeared in his notion of social justice. Gandhi was not in favour of western liberal ideas. Gandhi's concept of social justice included positive liberalism and democratic socialism. Being a traditionalist, Gandhi

supported varnashramadharma according to the Vedic sense. But he did not accept the varnashramadharma in its present sense. Gandhi argues about Varnashrama that, “*Varnashrama is, in my opinion, inherent in human nature and Hinduism has reduced it to a science. It does attach to birth...The division, however, into innumerable castes is unwarranted liberty taken with the doctrine.*”²⁹ Gandhi’s social and political ideas appeared in his famous weekly, *Harijan*. Its publication began in 1933, and it continued till 1947. The leading cause behind the publication of this weekly was the Poona pact of 1932.

Gandhi played a significant role in women’s emancipation. In his childhood, Gandhi was deeply influenced by his mother and found her a great teacher. Gandhi got understandings of spiritual life through his mother. In his political and social life, Kasturba influenced him a lot. Gandhi himself accepted the fact that he could not have done his political actions without the support of Kasturba. Gandhi’s political philosophy like, *Satyagraha*, *Ahimsa*, and self-discipline, were influenced by his wife. Gandhi accepts that ‘his philosophy of *Satyagraha* reflected the basic qualities of Kasturba’s character’. Gandhi further says that ‘I learned the message of non-violence from my wife’. Regarding his view on non-violence and self-discipline, Gandhi said, “*Without her, I could not have succeeded in my striving for ahimsa and self-discipline*”. *Gandhi accepted Kasturba’s importance and said that “She understood me better than anyone else.... her loyalty was matchless.*”³⁰ Gandhi tried to bring Indian masses into the nationalist movements; therefore, he directly connected himself with the masses. Many scholars like Bhikhu Parekh, Tanika Sarkar and Lyn Norvell etc., have explained women’s contribution to Gandhian movements. Tanika Sarkar is of the view that,

*“Gandhian movements changed this. Peasant women, upper-caste, middle-class women, upper-class Muslim women, tribal women came together in nationalist demonstrations, picketed foreign-goods shops, organized social boycotts of loyalists and public burning of foreign cloth, filled up prisons, become local level ‘dictators’ during civil disobedience when their men were arrested. No aspect of Gandhian politics was sexually segregated.”*³¹

During the Indian freedom struggle, Gandhi realised the importance of women’s role in the freedom struggle. He called women to join the freedom struggle, which led to the broader participation of women in public affairs. Gandhi considered epic heroines like Sita and Draupadi as an example of women’s capacity to face

adverse situations. Gandhi never saw the difference between men and women. For Gandhi, ‘men and women are of equal rank, but they are not identical.’ He further adds, ‘men are supreme in outward activities and the home life is entirely in the sphere of women’. Chakrabarty believes that Gandhi made women an integral part of the freedom struggle.³²

Gandhi also presented his view on civilization and criticised modern civilization. The present discourse on civilization is generally divided into three categories: the eastern civilization, western civilization, and modern civilization. According to Gandhi, there is no difference between the eastern civilization and western civilization, but it is the modern civilization that differentiates between them. Generally, western civilization is seen as modern civilization. According to Rajni Bakshi (2012), replacing ‘modern’ with ‘western’ was a deliberate, political act because the term ‘modern’ was originated in the west. Many times modernization and westernization are used interchangeably. And, according to Bakshi, Gandhi himself did so.³³ Gandhi did not accept western civilization as suitable for India. Despite making a difference between eastern and western civilization, Gandhi said that it is modernization that is separating western civilization from eastern civilization. For Gandhi, the West followed modern civilization which was materialistic and at that time, many Indians were also following the same modern materialistic civilization. Gandhi believed that the leading cause behind India’s subordination is not the British but the blind faith in modernization. Gandhi said, “It is not the British people who are ruling India, but it is modern civilization, through its railways, telegraphs, telephones, and almost every invention which has been claimed to be a triumph of civilization.”³⁴ Gandhi criticised almost every triumph of civilization because for Gandhi; railways, doctors, lawyers etc. have made their occupation polluted. They are not serving the people but they are just getting profit from the common people. Gandhi’s view on civilization was very clear. Gandhi’s understanding of civilization focuses on several fundamental questions like, what kind of society do we want to build? How can civilization build an egalitarian society? What, essentially, is good we see? In this way, Gandhi tried to build his definition of civilization based on ethics, morality and equality.

CONCLUSION:

When one goes through Gandhi’s entire political and social life, it appears that Gandhi was a visionary political leader who touched almost all aspects of human

life. Gandhi presented his extensive view not only in the political field but also in the socio-economic, and religious field. Even Gandhi touched on those issues that could influence human life, like environment and health as well. The important thing in Gandhi's life was that he did not differentiate between what he said and what he did? And, at the same time, Gandhi expected his political leaders to bring themselves with the common masses. Gandhi was not the first leader who led social movements in India, but he was the first leader who could connect many common masses with his movements. The main reason for getting large support of the common masses to Gandhi's movement was his emphasis on non-violence and ethics. For example, when Gandhi was leading peasant movements in Awadh, he suggested the peasants not use violence against the *zamindars* and *talukdars*. Gandhi gave more importance to non-violence because he was of the view that the violence would lead to further violence. And Indian common masses were not in the position of facing violence.

When Gandhi participated in the lower caste movements, he supported caste based on work (duty). Gandhi initiated a campaign for the removal of untouchability within Indian society. Though, there are many points where Gandhi could be criticized for example; when the earthquake hit Bihar in 1934, Gandhi said that Bihar is suffering from this natural disaster because they perform untouchability. Gandhi was criticized by Rabindranath Tagore for his statement. But suppose one tries to understand Gandhi's intention. In that case, it becomes clear that most of the Indians from different sections of the society at that time had deep faith in God and Gandhi wanted to realise to them that this disaster was the result of their sin, which they were performing in the form of untouchability. Gandhi considered culture and civilization important for human life. But he did not accept modern western civilization because he believed that modern western civilization was based on materialistic culture. He emphasized that ethics and humanistic principles should guide civilization. Gandhi also believed in gender equality and supported the participation of women in social and political activities. Because of his initiatives, Gandhi could get massive support from women in his socio-political movements.

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